

Experimental results and theoretical validation for the antioxidant mechanism of bilirubin[†]

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Manuscript received 15 December 2009, accepted 16 December 2009

Abstract : The present study demonstrates that hydroxyl, 1-hydroxy ethyl and glutathyl radicals abstract hydrogen atom from bilirubin and forms a carbon-centered radical. The bimolecular rate constant for the reaction of $\cdot\text{OH}$, 1-hydroxy ethyl and glutathyl radicals with bilirubin are 1.0×10^{10} , 2.0×10^8 and $6.0 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The transient absorption spectra obtained in these reactions have two peaks at 350 nm and 540 nm with bleaching in absorption at 450 nm. Both the absorption peaks form and decay with same rate constants showing that they are due to the same species. The bilirubin radical thus produced, decays with first order rate constant of $1.13 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$. In presence of oxygen the decay becomes faster confirming it to be a carbon-centered radical. Linoleic acid peroxy radical also reacts with bilirubin via hydrogen abstraction. In the case of $\text{NO}_2\cdot$ radical reaction, bilirubin produces absorption peak at 590 nm assigned to be the radical cation formed via single electron transfer from bilirubin. The bimolecular rate constant for this reaction is $2.0 \times 10^9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Corrected absorption spectra have been shown in few cases of these oxidation reactions. These results show that the oxidation of bilirubin can occur in two ways, either via hydrogen atom transfer or via single electron transfer depending on the nature of the oxidizing radical. *Ab initio* molecular orbital calculations have been performed to investigate the structure and energetics of radicals and radical cation produced by removal of hydrogen and electron, respectively from bilirubin molecule. It has been found that hydrogen abstraction from central methylenic group is most probable whereas pyrrole radical cation is most stable.

Keywords : Bilirubin, antioxidant mechanism, free radicals, hydrogen atom transfer, single electron transfer, pulse radiolysis, *ab initio* calculation.

Introduction

Bilirubin, a tetra pyrrole pigment and a toxic metabolite of heme was regarded as a waste to be excreted. An impaired excretion results in jaundice, a well recognizable symptom of liver disease. Even though, in 1959, bilirubin was reported to protect against the oxidation of lipids such as linoleic acid and vitamin A¹ only in 1987, Stocker *et al.* have shown very clearly that bilirubin (BR) can act as an antioxidant *in vivo* at a micromolar concentration and can inhibit lipid peroxidation initiated by peroxy radicals². Unconjugated BR as well as BR bound to albumin had also been shown to protect living system from hydroxyl, peroxy, hydroperoxy and superoxide

anion radicals^{3,4}. BR also has been reported to protect cells from neurotoxicity⁵ and myocardial ischemia⁶. A multiplied activity in the antioxidant effect of BR via a redox cycling involving BR-ROS-BV and biliverdin reductase has also been proposed⁷. Of late the potential function of BR and BV against the damaging effects of uncontrolled NO production has also been suggested⁸. All these studies endow with a motivation to study the reactions of BR with bio-relevant free radicals in order to understand the mechanistic pathway.

The mechanism for the reaction of BR with oxidizing radicals as reported so far is the following. The hydroxyl radical on reacting with BR forms a tetrapyrrole pigment (absorbing at 570 nm), via a radical adduct absorbing at

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

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540 nm⁹. Radicals like N₃[•], Br₂^{•-}, CCl₃OO[•] form the BR radical cation (absorbing at 585 nm)^{10,11} via single electron transfer (SET) mechanism. Hatfield and Barclay¹² argued in favour of SET mechanism. Their result agrees well with the earlier literature on peroxy radical reaction of BR¹¹. The said radicals are not regarded as physiologically relevant. In the present paper we report a detailed mechanistic study for the reaction of BR with hydroxyl, glutathyl, linoleic acid peroxy and nitrogen dioxide radicals. Our study demonstrates that hydroxyl, glutathyl and methyl radicals abstract hydrogen from BR and forms a carbon-centered radical. Reaction of linoleic acid peroxy radical has been studied to mimic lipid peroxy (LOO[•]) radical and it is seen that, in contrast to CCl₃OO[•] radical¹¹, LOO[•] interacts via hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) mechanism. However, in the case of NO₂[•] radical reaction, BR radical cation is produced via SET from BR.

Materials and methods :

Bilirubin was from Sigma and was purified by the procedure described elsewhere¹³. Glutathione and DTNB were from Sigma-Aldrich, ethanol from E. Merck and were used as received. All other chemicals were of AR grade. The solvent used was freshly prepared de-ionised 'nanopure' water (conductivity < 0.06 μS cm⁻¹) obtained from a Barnstead nano-pure cartridge filtration system (Barnstead Corp., Boston, MA, USA). BR solution (in 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ NaOH) was prepared just prior to the experiment. All the experiments were carried out in dim light condition to prevent photoionization of BR.

Pulse radiolysis :

The pulse radiolysis system using 7 MeV electrons has been described earlier¹⁴. The dosimetry was carried out using an air-saturated aqueous solution containing 5

× 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ KSCN assuming G_e for (SCN)₂^{•-} = 23889 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ per 100 eV at 500 nm¹⁵. The kinetic spectrophotometric detection system covered the wavelength range from 250 to 800 nm. Alkaline pH was obtained by adding NaOH only. High purity (> 99.9%) N₂O, from BOC India Pvt. Ltd. was used as per requirement. The following reactions occur after irradiation in the reaction medium used.

The bimolecular rate constants were calculated by plotting the pseudo-first order rates of formation of the transients against the concerned solute concentrations. The uncertainty in the measurement in bimolecular rate constant was < 10%.

Computational methods :

Ab initio molecular orbital calculations have been used to investigate the structures and energetics of ground state and different radical species of bilirubin. Three radical species have been considered corresponding to hydrogen abstraction from central methylenic group (1) and the pyrrole groups, which are closer (2) and farther (3) from the methylenic group on one side. The ground state geometries of the species have been fully optimized at the Hartree-Fock level of theory using 6-31G(d) basis set. All the calculations in this work have been done using the GAMESS electronic structure programme. Partial atomic charges as well as atomic spin densities have been calculated using Mulliken population analysis scheme as implemented in the GAMESS electronic structure programme¹⁶. To account for the effect of solvent, self-consistent-reaction-field calculations have also been carried out using polarizable continuum model for the solvent.

Results and discussion

Reaction with hydroxyl radical (OH[•]) :

Albeit in a real physiological situation the OH[•] radical disappears almost instantly at the site of its generation,

the reaction of this radical still considered as a very important aspect and needs to be attended. Fig. 1 depicts the transient absorption spectra obtained in the reaction

Fig. 1. Transient absorption spectra recorded for a N_2O -saturated aqueous solution containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ bilirubin at pH 8.5. (a) 20 μs , (b) 200 μs , (c) 1000 μs , (d) 1800 μs after the electron pulse.

Inset : Differential absorption versus time plot for the BR radical obtained from the solution as described in Fig.-2. (A) Recorded at 350 nm. (a) only N_2O -saturated solution, (b) mixture of 1 cc N_2O -saturated and 4 cc air-saturated solution. (B) Recorded at 540 nm. (a) only N_2O -saturated solution, (b) mixture of 1 cc N_2O -saturated and 4 cc air-saturated solution.

of hydroxyl radical with BR. Absorption peaks at 375 nm and 540 nm with bleaching spectra at 400–500 nm at 20 μs are evident. The bimolecular rate constant for the formation of both the absorption peaks is $1 \times 10^{10} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This numerical value agrees well with that reported earlier⁹ where the peak at 540 nm was assigned to a hydroxyl radical adduct. As time progresses the absorption peak at 540 nm decreases and shifts towards red side. This phenomenon was earlier suggested as formation of a tetra pyrrole product. The decay constant of the transients absorbing at 375 nm and 540 nm are also same being $1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ suggesting that they are due to the same species.

The decay of the BR radical has shown in the insets of Fig. 1. In presence of $\sim 20\%$ oxygen introduced with

N_2O , the decay at 540 nm becomes faster (Inset, Fig. 1B). This result suggests that the absorption peak at 540 nm is due to a carbon centered radical. In Fig. 1A, the oxygen effect on the radical absorbing at 350 nm has been shown. It is evident that in presence of oxygen the decay of the radical becomes faster with the appearance of a new absorption that continues to increase up to a time scale of 1.5 ms. This increase in absorption is probably due to formation of another species.

Reaction with glutathyl radical (GS^\bullet) :

Thiols are present in living systems which, in addition to participating in cellular redox processes (reaction 8), also take part in scavenging free radicals (reaction 9). The antioxidant action of the thiols is attributed to the latter reaction.

Both the reactions generate thiyl radicals (RS^\bullet), which, in turn, can act as reactive oxidants as they are able to initiate lipid peroxidation by abstracting the bis-allylic hydrogen from poly-unsaturated fatty acids¹⁷. Further, the thiyl radicals can also add to the lipid double bond leading to efficient *cis/trans* isomerization of mono- and poly-unsaturated fatty acids¹⁸. Hence, their repair is necessary both for their storage as efficient antioxidants and protection of lipids from thiyl radical induced denaturation. To this end, the reaction of BR with the thiyl radicals derived from the cellular antioxidant glutathione (GSH) was followed by pulse radiolysis. The reaction led to a transient spectrum with absorption maximum at 540 nm with bleaching in the 400–500 nm region.

It is known that at a pH > 7 , the thiyl radicals can associate with the parent anion to furnish the $RSSR^{\bullet-}$ radical according to the following equilibrium¹⁹,

However, under the present experimental conditions (pH < 6), we are justified in ignoring the contribution from the $RSSR^{\bullet-}$ radical. In order to confirm this, a blank experiment was also carried out without BR at pH 6 using the same dose rate. As expected, no signal for $RSSR^{\bullet-}$ was detected under the experimental conditions.

In this study we have generated thiyl radical as mentioned in the materials and methods section and the reaction of this radical has been studied with BR. The transient absorption spectra recorded from an aqueous-ethanolic (50% v/v) solution containing $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ BR, $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ GSH at pH 6.4 is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Transient absorption spectra recorded for a N_2O -saturated ethanolic-aqueous (9 : 1, v/v) solution containing 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} bilirubin, 2×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} GSH at pH 6.4. (a) 50 μs , (b) 100 μs , (c) 500 μs after the electron pulse.

Inset : Differential absorption versus time plot for the BR radical obtained from the solution as described in Fig. 2. Recorded at 530 nm. (a) only N_2O -saturated solution, (b) mixture of 1 cc N_2O -saturated and 4 cc air-saturated solution.

This shows absorption maximum at 540 nm and bleaching at 400–500 nm region, growing up to 500 μs after the electron pulse. The bimolecular rate constant for the formation of the absorption peak at 540 nm is 6×10^8 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1} . Thiyl radicals are known to react via hydrogen abstraction and also addition to double bonds. Here in this case the absorption peak can be assigned from the previous sections of our study as due to a carbon centered radical which can be formed via hydrogen abstraction from BR. The BR radical does not decay (line a, Inset of Fig. 2) up to a time scale of 1 ms. However, in presence of oxygen the radical starts decaying after 300 μs of the electron pulse (line b, Inset of Fig. 2). The results in this study can explain the fact reported earlier⁸ that bile pigments and thiol groups can compete and/or synergise the cellular defense against NO-related species. Thiols can scavenge the NO-related radicals and becomes thiyl radical, which in turn can be repaired by BR.

Reaction with 1-hydroxy ethyl radical ($CH_3\dot{C}HOH$) :

Hepatic drug metabolic pathways catalyzed by the cytochrome P450 (CYP) system. CYP oxidizes ethanol, to generate reactive products including 1-hydroxy ethyl radical, which activates various agents to generate further reactive oxygen species. Bilirubin is present in liver and so its reaction with ethanol derived radical (generated in liver) becomes necessary. With this view we have studied the reaction of 1-hydroxy ethyl radical with bilirubin.

The transient absorption spectra recorded from an aqueous-ethanolic (50% v/v) solution containing 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} BR, at pH 7.6 is shown in Fig. 3. As it is seen in this case also two absorption peaks are evident. It seems that the reaction pathway is similar to that of hydroxyl radical reaction. Another point to note is that bilirubin can scavenge the ethanol derived radicals very efficiently, the bimolecular rate constant for the reaction being 2.0×10^8 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1} .

Fig. 3. The transient absorption spectra recorded from an N_2O -saturated aqueous-ethanol (50% v/v) solution containing 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} BR, at pH 7.6. (a) 100 μs , (b) 150 μs , (c) 220 μs after the electron pulse.

Reaction with linoleic acid peroxy radical (LOO^\bullet) :

Linoleic acid is an important lipid component and prevention of its peroxidation is also an excellent criterion for an efficient antioxidant²⁰. In the present study, it was observed that at pH 12, BR could react with the linoleic acid peroxy radical generated by pulse radiolysis. It is of no surprise, as BR is already known¹ to protect lipids

from peroxidation. Under the experimental conditions (pH 12), even when the linoleate ions exist as negatively charged micelles, their reaction with BR produced the same transient absorption peak at 540 nm. The spectrum in this case was recorded in the wavelength region between 520–600 nm. The kinetic trace at 540 nm (Fig. 4) shows the formation of the BR radical in the first part probably via direct interaction with hydroxyl radical and the slow build up at later stage is via the reaction with LOO^\bullet radical. In earlier report it was observed that the so-called representative peroxy radical ($\text{CCl}_3\text{OO}^\bullet$) reacts with BR causing one electron oxidation and produces a radical cation. On the contrary lipid peroxy radicals causes hydrogen atom abstraction while reacting with BR.

Fig. 4. Differential absorption versus time plot for the BR radical recorded at 540 nm from the solution (saturated with N_2O : air 4 : 1) containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ bilirubin, $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ linoleic acid at pH 12.

Reaction with nitrogen dioxide radical (NO_2^\bullet) :

The oxides of nitrogen such as NO_2^\bullet and NO^\bullet , released in cigarette smoke and other sources are known for their deleterious effects²¹. In particular, NO_2^\bullet is known to abstract H-atoms from unsaturated lipids, thereby acting as an initiator of lipid peroxidation. It is also known that NO_2^\bullet radical can form adduct in addition to causing isomerization of arachidonic acid²². Thus, understanding the mechanism of the reaction of BR with this radical becomes indispensable. On pulse-irradiating a $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ BR, $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ nitrite anion, N_2O -saturated aqueous solution at pH 9.2, NO_2^\bullet radicals ($E =$

1.03 V vs NHE) were initially formed via reaction, 1, 2 and 8. These NO_2^\bullet radicals subsequently reacted with BR to yield a transient spectrum (Fig. 5) with absorption maximum at 580 nm fully developed at 40 ms after the electron pulse. The bimolecular rate constant for the formation of this radical cation as measured at 580 nm is $2 \times 10^9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. In general, hydrogen abstraction reactions for NO_2^\bullet radical mediated oxidation of bio molecules are much slower²³ than this value.

Fig. 5. Transient absorption spectra recorded for a N_2O -saturated aqueous solution containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ bilirubin, $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaNO_2 at pH 9.2. (a) 5 μs , (b) 20 μs , (c) 40 μs , (d) 80 μs after the electron pulse.

Correction of the observed bilirubin radical spectra :

The difference absorption spectra of the bilirubin radicals were corrected for the depletion of the parents and corrected spectra are presented where the molar extinction coefficients were plotted against wavelength by applying a correction for the parent depletion. At a given wavelength, molar extinction coefficient (ϵ_R) of the bilirubin radicals could be calculated from the following equation :

$$\epsilon_R = \epsilon_G + \frac{\Delta \text{OD}_{\text{obsd}} \cdot (\epsilon_G)_{\text{dose}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{dose}} \cdot G_R}$$

where OD_{dose} is the optical density of $(\text{SCN})_2^{\bullet-}$ radical at 500 nm observed in the thiocyanate dosimetry. $G_R = 6.5$, ϵ_R and ϵ_G are the molar extinction coefficients for the bilirubin radicals and the parent respectively. Corrected spectra for the radicals are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Corrected absorption spectra of the bilirubin radicals in different cases of oxidation. (a) Glutathyl radical, (b) 1-hydroxy ethyl radical, (c) hydroxyl radical, (d) nitrogen dioxide radical induced oxidation.

As it is seen, in case of oxidation 1 hydroxy ethyl and glutathyl radicals the absorption maximum as well as the shape of the spectra matches well. The difference in the peak position in hydroxyl radical induced oxidation with that in glutathyl radical induced oxidation is due to the change in medium. In case of NO_2^* radical reaction, both the shape as well as peak position are different in comparison to other cases. In this case an additional peak at ~ 590 nm is evident. Thus we can infer that in the oxidation reaction of bilirubin two types of radicals are produced depending on the nature of the oxidizing radicals.

Computational results :

Even though the aforesaid experimental results provide an unambiguous representation for the reaction mechanism for the oxidation of BR, we have further substantiated these findings by DFT-based quantum chemical calculations. The probability of HAT from the central carbon atom (1) in comparison to HAT from two types of nitrogen (closest and farthest with respect to that carbon) of pyrroles (2 and 3) has been examined (Fig. 7). Atomic charges and the atomic spin density for these three radical species, along with the ground state parent (BRH) have been calculated.

The atoms having highest unpaired electron (spin) density in the radical species and the relative energy required to produce various radical species are shown in Table 1. The order of relative energy ($\Delta E_{\text{formation}}$) has

Neutral parent (BRH)

(1) Hydrogen abstraction from C(10)H₂

(2) Hydrogen abstraction from N-H of nearest pyrrole

(3) Hydrogen abstraction from N-H of farthest pyrrole

Fig. 7. Optimized structure of neutral bilirubin parent and its radical species.

been evaluated through hydrogen detachment from various positions using the ground state parent molecule geometry. The $\Delta E_{\text{formation}}$ has been considered as the energy

Table 1. Position of spin density and energetics for various processes

Species	$\Delta E_{\text{formation}}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Position of highest spin density	$\Delta E_{\text{relaxed}}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
			Gas phase	Water
1	0.0	C (10)	32.24	34.35
2	29.35	C (6, 8, 9)	0.0	0.0
3	41.89	C (5, 7, 9)	26.18	26.09

difference between the parent and the respective radicals obtained after detaching hydrogen atom vertically from the parent and keeping remaining portion of the geometry unchanged. The relative energies of the three relaxed radicals at their respective optimized geometries (denoted as $\Delta E_{\text{relaxed}}$) in the absence and presence of water have also been calculated (Table 1). It is evident from the second column in Table 1 that least amount of energy is required to remove a hydrogen atom from central methylenic carbon to produce a carbon-centered radical (1). The processes producing nitrogen-centered radicals on pyrrole group require relatively more energy. The data suggests that the first step of hydrogen abstraction from BRH produces carbon-centered radical on the central methylenic group. Carbon-centered radical species 1 has almost all spin density (0.866) localized on atom C (10). Spin densities for nitrogen-centered radicals 2 and 3 are delocalized over the surrounding carbon atoms. High spin densities have been found on C (6), C (8) and C (9) atoms for 2 and C (5), C (7), C (9) atoms for 3. It should be noted that even on abstraction of hydrogen atom from N-H bond of pyrrole, spin densities (unpaired electrons) are higher on carbon atoms but not on nitrogen atom. Furthermore, abstraction of hydrogen atom from N-H bond of pyrrole and C-H bond of methylenic group produce delocalized and localized unpaired electron densities, respectively. The delocalized unpaired electron on radical species 2 and 3 should react slowly and hence selectively, whereas localized unpaired electron on radical species 1 should react non-selectively. This is also reflected in the relative energies (stabilities) of these three relaxed radical species in the absence and presence of water (solvent), $2 < 3 < 1$.

On the basis of *ab initio* calculations it can be inferred that on abstraction of hydrogen atom from BR carbon

(10)-centered radical (1) is produced relatively easily but abstraction of hydrogen atom from N-H bond of pyrroles produces a more stable radical. It might also be inferred that in the first step carbon-centered radical (1) is formed, which after relaxation transforms into the most stable radical species 2.

To summarize, kinetic spectrophotometric technique has been employed to understand the mechanism of bilirubin oxidation. It has been observed that the site of oxidation depends on the nature of the oxidizing radicals. In the case of one electron oxidants the formation probability of a pyrrole radical cation is sure. If the radicals have hydrogen abstraction ability, a carbon centered radical at the central methylenic group is evident.

Acknowledgement

At the outset the authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. Jai Pal Mittal for his constant inspiration. We thank Dr. S. K. Sarkar, Head, Radiation and Photochemistry Division for encouragement and support. We also thank Shri S. A. Nadkarni and his team for technical help in carrying out pulse radiolysis studies.

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